

Supplementary Information for Off-Policy Evaluation in Two-Stage Recommender Systems via Latent Distribution Alignment

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Supplementary material. The online appendix is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20690139>.

1 Proofs

This appendix provides proofs of the theoretical results stated in the main text.

1.1 Proof of Proposition 1 (Upper Bound on Approximation Bias)

Proof. We expand the expectation of the LPAIPS estimator. Define the proxy reward on the logging side as

$$\bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z) := \frac{\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_0(x)} \pi_0(a | \mathcal{A}_0, x) p_\theta(z | x, a) q(x, a)}{\bar{\pi}_{0,\theta}(z | x)} \quad (\text{S1})$$

(where we set $\bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z) := 0$ when $\bar{\pi}_{0,\theta}(z | x) = 0$). By expanding the importance weights, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{R}_{\text{LPAIPS}}] = \mathbb{E}_x \left[\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \bar{\pi}_{1,\theta}(z | x) \bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z) \right] =: R_{0,\theta}(\mathcal{A}_1, \pi). \quad (\text{S2})$$

Similarly, under the same convention, define the proxy reward on the target side as

$$\bar{q}_{1,\theta}(x, z) := \frac{\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_1(x)} \pi(a | \mathcal{A}_1, x) p_\theta(z | x, a) q(x, a)}{\bar{\pi}_{1,\theta}(z | x)}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

Using $\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} p_\theta(z | x, a) = 1$ and exchanging the order of summation, the true expected reward of the target policy can be written as:

$$R(\mathcal{A}_1, \pi) = \mathbb{E}_x \left[\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \bar{\pi}_{1,\theta}(z | x) \bar{q}_{1,\theta}(x, z) \right]. \quad (\text{S4})$$

Therefore, the difference between the estimator's expectation and the true value is upper bounded as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} |R_{0,\theta} - R(\mathcal{A}_1, \pi)| &= \left| \mathbb{E}_x \left[\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \bar{\pi}_{1,\theta}(z | x) (\bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z) - \bar{q}_{1,\theta}(x, z)) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}_x \left[\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \bar{\pi}_{1,\theta}(z | x) |\bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z) - \bar{q}_{1,\theta}(x, z)| \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S5})$$

Now, consider a fixed (x, z) . Both $\bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z)$ and $\bar{q}_{1,\theta}(x, z)$ are convex combinations of the expected rewards $\{q(x, a)\}$ over the set $\mathcal{A}_\theta(x, z) = \{a \in \mathcal{A}_0(x) \cup \mathcal{A}_1(x) \mid p_\theta(z | x, a) > 0\}$. Since the difference between any two convex combinations is upper bounded by the maximum difference among the underlying values,

$$|\bar{q}_{0,\theta}(x, z) - \bar{q}_{1,\theta}(x, z)| \leq \Delta_\theta(x, z) \quad (\text{S6})$$

holds. Squaring yields Eq. (13). In particular, when reward sufficiency (Definition 1) is satisfied, $\Delta_\theta(x, z) = 0$, for all (x, z) , and $\text{Bias}^2 = 0$ is recovered.

Remark 1 (Conservativeness of the bias bound). The reward variation $\Delta_\theta(x, z)$ is defined as the maximum reward difference over all actions with $p_\theta(z | x, a) > 0$. Under soft assignment, actions with negligible encoder probability still contribute to this worst-case measure, making the bound conservative in practice. Accordingly, Proposition 1 should be interpreted as a worst-case characterization of the source of approximation bias rather than a tight bound on the actual bias.

1.2 Proof of Theorem 1 (Latent Overlap Control Theorem)

Proof. For each $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, let $\mu_z := \mathbb{E}[g_z(X)]$ and $\sigma_z^2 := \text{Var}(g_z(X))$. By Cantelli's inequality (the one-sided Chebyshev inequality) for any random variable, for any $\alpha < \mu_z$:

$$\Pr(g_z(X) < \alpha) \leq \frac{\sigma_z^2}{\sigma_z^2 + (\mu_z - \alpha)^2}. \quad (\text{S7})$$

By condition (C1), $\mu_z \geq \mu_{\min}$, and by condition (C2), $\sigma_z^2 \leq \sigma^2$. Since the function $f(v, m) = v/(v + (m - \alpha)^2)$ is monotonically increasing in $v > 0$ and monotonically decreasing in $m > \alpha$, the upper bound can be relaxed as:

$$\frac{\sigma_z^2}{\sigma_z^2 + (\mu_z - \alpha)^2} \leq \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + (\mu_{\min} - \alpha)^2}. \quad (\text{S8})$$

Finally, since $\{\min_z g_z(X) < \alpha\} = \bigcup_{z=1}^K \{g_z(X) < \alpha\}$, applying the union bound yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr\left(\min_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} g_z(X) < \alpha\right) &\leq \sum_{z=1}^K \Pr(g_z(X) < \alpha) \\ &\leq \frac{K\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + (\mu_{\min} - \alpha)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S9})$$

Since probabilities take values in $[0, 1]$, letting $\delta(\alpha) := \min\left\{1, \frac{K\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + (\mu_{\min} - \alpha)^2}\right\}$ yields Eq. (15). Note that this theorem controls the probability over all latent classes $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, providing a sufficient condition (a stronger form) for Definition 2, which targets only the classes supported by the target policy.

Remark on variance control via clipping. When $\delta(\alpha) > 0$, the bound in Eq. (16) does not necessarily hold directly. In practice, one may instead use the clipped estimator

$$\hat{R}_{\text{LPAIPS}}^{\text{clip}} := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \min\left(w_\theta(x_i, z_i), \frac{1}{\alpha}\right) r_i. \quad (\text{S10})$$

This clips large importance weights and yields unconditional variance control at the cost of additional bias that depends on $\delta(\alpha)$.

1.3 Marginal Support under MMD Alignment

As described in Section 6, when the Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) is used as the distributional distance to align the latent marginal distribution $P_{0,\theta}$ of the logging policy with the uniform distribution U , the following corollary holds with respect to condition (C1) of Theorem 1.

Corollary 1 (Marginal Support under MMD Alignment). *Let $\lambda_{\min} > 0$ be the minimum eigenvalue of the kernel matrix \mathbf{K} . If $\text{MMD}_k^2(P_{0,\theta}, U) \leq \varepsilon$, then the average lower bound μ_{\min} satisfies:*

$$\mu_{\min} \geq \max\left\{0, \frac{1}{K} - \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda_{\min}}}\right\}. \quad (\text{S11})$$

Proof. Let $p_z := P_{0,\theta}(z)$, $u_z := 1/K$, and denote the probability vectors as $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_K)^\top$ and $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_K)^\top$. Since $\mathcal{Z} = \{1, \dots, K\}$ is a finite set, the mean embeddings in the RKHS using the feature map $\phi : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ are expressed as finite sums $\mu_P = \sum_{z=1}^K p_z \phi(z)$ and $\mu_U = \sum_{z=1}^K u_z \phi(z)$. Therefore, the squared MMD expands as:

$$\text{MMD}_k^2(P_{0,\theta}, U) = (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u})^\top \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}) \geq \lambda_{\min} \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}\|_2^2, \quad (\text{S12})$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{zz'} = k(z, z')$ is the positive definite kernel matrix and $\lambda_{\min} > 0$ is its minimum eigenvalue. From the assumption $\text{MMD}_k^2(P_{0,\theta}, U) \leq \varepsilon$, it follows that $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}\|_2 \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon/\lambda_{\min}}$. Since $|p_z - u_z| \leq \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}\|_2$ for each coordinate,

$$\mu_{\min} = \min_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} p_z \geq \frac{1}{K} - \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda_{\min}}}. \quad (\text{S13})$$

Since probability mass is non-negative, we obtain $\mu_{\min} \geq \max\left\{0, \frac{1}{K} - \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda_{\min}}}\right\}$.

1.4 Marginal Support under KL Alignment

Implementation details for KL alignment. The theoretical objective in Eq. (18) is written in terms of the marginal divergence $\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U)$, where $P_{0,\theta}(z)$ denotes the marginal latent distribution induced by the logging data. In the practical implementation of LPAIPS-KL, we optimize the tractable surrogate

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}_{(x,a)\sim S} [\text{KL}(p_\theta(\cdot | x, a) \| U)] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{(x,a)\sim S, z\sim p_\theta(\cdot | x, a)} [\log p_\theta(z | x, a) + \log K]. \end{aligned}$$

By the convexity of KL divergence, $\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U) \leq \mathbb{E}_{(x,a)\sim S} [\text{KL}(p_\theta(\cdot | x, a) \| U)]$, so the implemented objective minimizes an upper bound on the marginal KL alignment term. When used without Spectral Normalization, this KL surrogate coincides with the KL regularizer used in LIPS [16].

Since the implemented KL surrogate upper-bounds $\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U)$, controlling the former also controls the latter. Under the condition $\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U) \leq \varepsilon$, Pinsker’s inequality yields the following lower bound on the minimum marginal mass.

Corollary 2 (Marginal Support under KL Alignment). *If $\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U) \leq \varepsilon$, then the average lower bound μ_{\min} satisfies:*

$$\mu_{\min} \geq \max\left\{0, \frac{1}{K} - \sqrt{2\varepsilon}\right\}. \quad (\text{S14})$$

Proof. Using Pinsker’s inequality $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}\|_1 \leq \sqrt{2\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U)}$, under the assumption $\text{KL}(P_{0,\theta}\|U) \leq \varepsilon$, we have $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}\|_1 \leq \sqrt{2\varepsilon}$. By the property of the L_1 norm, for each coordinate $|p_z - 1/K| \leq \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}\|_1 \leq \sqrt{2\varepsilon}$, so

$$\mu_{\min} = \min_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} p_z \geq \frac{1}{K} - \sqrt{2\varepsilon}. \quad (\text{S15})$$

Since probability mass is non-negative, we obtain $\mu_{\min} \geq \max\{0, 1/K - \sqrt{2\varepsilon}\}$.

Remark 2 (Comparison of MMD and KL). MMD leverages the geometric structure of the RKHS through the minimum eigenvalue λ_{\min} of the kernel matrix, evaluating deviation in the L_2 norm. On the other hand, the KL divergence evaluates deviation in the L_1 norm via Pinsker’s inequality and, due to the constraints of the probability simplex, may help suppress the tendency of probability mass to concentrate on sparse categories.

1.5 Variance Control via Spectral Normalization

As described in Section 6, SN is applied to all networks. For the encoder in particular, this provides a theoretical basis for satisfying condition (C2) of Theorem 1. Specifically, the following lemma holds.

Lemma 1 (Variance Upper Bound via Spectral Normalization). *Suppose the encoder $p_\theta(z | x, a)$ is L -Lipschitz continuous with respect to the input (x, a) , and the diameter of the input feature space is bounded by D . Then the variance of the per-context latent probability mass in condition (C2) of Theorem 1 is upper bounded as:*

$$\text{Var}(g_z(X)) \leq \frac{\min\{1, (LD)^2\}}{4}. \quad (\text{S16})$$

Proof. First, by the law of total variance, $\text{Var}(\mathbb{E}[Y | X]) \leq \text{Var}(Y)$ holds for any random variable, so

$$\text{Var}(g_z(X)) = \text{Var}(\mathbb{E}[p_\theta(z | X, A) | X]) \leq \text{Var}(p_\theta(z | X, A)) \quad (\text{S17})$$

holds. Next, since the encoder function p_θ is L -Lipschitz continuous and the diameter of the input space is D , the maximum difference in the output for any input is upper bounded by LD . Furthermore, since the range of p_θ is contained in the interval $[0, 1]$ as it represents a probability, the range of the random variable $Y = p_\theta(z | X, A)$ is at most $\min\{1, LD\}$. Finally, applying Popoviciu’s inequality for bounded random variables ($\text{Var}(Y) \leq (\sup Y - \inf Y)^2/4$) yields

$$\text{Var}(g_z(X)) \leq \frac{\min\{1, (LD)^2\}}{4}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

SN controls the Lipschitz constant L by constraining the maximum singular value of the weight matrices of the network, thereby shrinking $\text{Var}(g_z(X))$ and satisfying the requirement of condition (C2).

Remark 3 (Theoretical status of spectral normalization). Lemma 1 establishes that controlling the Lipschitz constant of the encoder via SN yields an upper bound on $\text{Var}(g_z(X))$, thereby motivating its use for satisfying condition (C2). However, this connection should be interpreted as providing theoretical motivation rather than a complete characterization of practical training dynamics, where factors such as optimization trajectories and the interplay with other loss terms also play a role.